

and 22 kg P/ha (triple superphosphate) was applied at 4 depths. Urea (200 kg N/ha) and muriate of potash (25 kg K/ha) were broadcast. Remaining N was top-dressed at panicle initiation. Three replications were harvested at panicle initiation to record root and shoot dry weight and N, P, and K uptake. Grain yield was recorded for the remaining three replications.

Root and shoot dry weight and grain yield significantly increased for both varieties at 5-cm placement depth. Placing P at 10 and 15 cm decreased dry weights and grain yield (see table).

The linear relationship of root dry weight and dry yield had a highly significant correlation coefficient of 0.980 for both IR42 and MR7, indicating that placing P at the proper root zone enhanced root growth and increased grain yield. N, P, and K uptake was greater at 0 and 5 cm placement depths than at 10 and 15 cm, indicating that nutrients are utilized most effectively by plant roots when P is placed in their immediate vicinity (see figure). □

Effect of P placement depths on root and shoot dry weight at panicle initiation and yield of wetland rice, Sabah, East Malaysia.

Placement depth (cm)	IR42			MR7		
	Root dry wt (g/pot)	Shoot dry wt (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)	Root dry wt (g/pot)	Shoot dry wt (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)
0	3.7 b	22.85 b	155.6 b	3.6 b	27.41 b	154.5 b
5	4.3 a	25.77 a	165.8 a	4.4 a	30.32 a	166.0 a
10	3.5 b	21.30 c	153.1 c	3.5 b	24.3 c	152.8 c
15	3.2 bc	20.70 c	150.2 d	3.1 bc	24.10 c	150.8 d

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 0.05 level.

Changes in nutrient uptake by wetland rice at different depths of phosphorus placement at panicle initiation, Sabah, East Malaysia.

Response of prerelease rice cultures to nitrogen in light-textured soil

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A field trial during 1980 kharif (wet season) studied the response to nitrogen levels of four prerelease rices (Table 1) on a red sandy loam with low organic matter and phosphorus, moderate potash, and pH of 6.1. IR20 was the check variety. The treatments were replicated four times in a split-plot design with variety on the main plots and nitrogen levels on the subplots. A basal application of 22 kg P and 42 kg K per hectare was given. Nitrogen was applied 50% at transplanting, 25% at 25 days after transplanting (DT), and 25% at 45 DT.

IET2490 and IET2730 responded significantly up to 120 kg N/ha; KMP39 response leveled off beyond 80 kg N/ha (Table 2). All cultures except Mandya Vani were superior to IR20. □

Table 1. Characteristics of rices tested in Mandya, India.

Culture	Cross	Duration (days)	1,000-grain wt (g)
Mandya Vani	IR8/CR1014	128	17
IR20	IR262/TKM6	131	19
KMP39	Jaya/W1263	140	20
IET2730	IR8/Annapurna	141	32
IET2490	IR8/NP130	143	30

Table 2. Response of prerelease rice cultures to nitrogen in Mandya, India.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	Mandya Vani	IET2490	ET2730	KMP39	IR20
0	2.4	3.0	3.0	3.2	2.4
40	3.2	4.1	4.0	3.9	3.7
80	3.7	4.8	4.8	4.2	4.1
120	3.8	5.2	5.1	4.4	4.5
160	3.6	4.8	5.0	4.5	4.6
CD (0.05)	Varieties: 0.36		Nitrogen: 0.33		Interaction: NS
Cv (%)	11				

Methods of zinc application to rice on sodic soil

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Zinc (Zn) deficiency is a widespread nutritional disorder of rice, particularly in sodic soils under reclamation. A field experiment to correct the problem was carried out on Ghabdan loam soil (salic Natraqualf) in Sangrur district of Punjab.

The soil at the site had pH 10.3, 0.08% organic carbon, 1.25% calcium carbonate, 80.4% exchangeable sodium, and 0.52 ppm available Zn. The treatments are in the table.

Before the experiment, 50% of the gypsum requirement was mixed in the 15 cm soil layer of all the plots. Thirty-day-old PR106 rice seedlings were transplanted to submerged soils in all plots and fertilized with 120 kg N/ha as urea and 26 kg P/ha as superphosphate.

Rice plants grew poorly in control plots and exhibited typical Zn deficiency symptoms. Zinc application, irrespective of method, caused significant increase in grain yield and increased Zn content of 40-day-old leaves, straw, and grain (see table). Soil application of ZnSO₄ before transplanting produced maximum grain yield (140% over control). Topdressing ZnSO₄ 7 or 15 days after transplanting produced similar grain yield. Foliar spray of 1% or 2% ZnSO₄ solution increased

Effect of methods of zinc application on zinc content and rice grain yield.^a

Treatment	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Increase (%) Over control	Zinc content (ppm)		
			Leaf ^c	Straw	Grain
Root dip					
2% ZnO suspension	3.2	74	15.1	16.3	9.9
4% ZnO suspension	3.3	81	15.7	17.1	10.4
Foliar sprays (3)					
1% ZnSO ₄ solution	2.5	38	16.2	14.2	9.4
2% ZnSO ₄ solution	2.8	55	16.7	15.1	9.7
Root dip + foliar sprays (2)					
2% ZnO suspension + 1% ZnSO ₄	3.9	115	18.6	17.6	10.6
4% ZnO suspension + 1% ZnSO ₄	4.1	126	19.8	18.4	11.0
Soil application of 50 kg ZnSO ₄ /ha					
Before transplanting	4.3	140	17.6	18.8	12.2
7 days after transplanting	4.2	133	17.1	19.3	11.9
15 days after transplanting	4.0	123	16.2	18.5	11.2
Control	1.8	—	10.8	11.7	8.9
CD at 5%	0.4	—	0.9	0.9	1.0

^aAv of 3 replications. ^bOven-dry basis. ^cForty-day-old.

yield significantly over the control, but was inferior to all other methods of zinc application. Dipping rice seedling roots in

a 4% ZnO suspension supplemented with foliar sprays of 1% ZnSO₄ solution gave yields similar to ZnSO₄ application. □

Environment and its influence

Low water temperature and sterility in rice

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Rice plants are most sensitive to low temperature during meiosis or when the auricle distance between the flag leaf and the leaf immediately below is zero. Low temperature at this stage usually causes high spikelet sterility. In some rice growing areas, fields are flooded above the growing point of plants to protect them from cold air temperature at night. Irrigation water is warmer than ambient air and protects the growing point from cold night air.

In some rice growing areas, however, irrigation water is cooler than the air temperature. Tests in Chuncheon, Korea, showed that 17°C water temperature can cause 100% sterility (see figure). However, water depth and plant height or position of the growing point during

Sterility of rice cultivars treated with low water temperature at different stages of panicle development.